

HISTORY OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract: This work analyses about Intercultural Communication and history of this communication. The aim of the work is to find out the role and Intercultural Communication in society and to give information about origin of intercultural communication. It includes information on the definition and origin of Intercultural Communication and provides information about the history of communication, culture and basic concepts of Intercultural communication and its role in various aspects of life. This article also includes information about the terms of culture, communication, Multiculturalism, interpersonal communication.

Key words: Intercultural communication, multiculturalism, interpersonal communication, history, research.

Intercultural Communication means information from many social groups, including those with various educational, social, ethnic, and religious origins, is shared through intercultural dialogue. It aims to comprehend the variations in behavior, communication, and worldview among individuals from various cultural backgrounds.

Mastering a foreign language is only part of the package. Understanding the other person's cultural background, values, and beliefs also requires understanding. Intercultural communication skills are essential here. They are necessary for successfully communicating with people from other cultures and social groups. Intercultural communication skills also include a willingness to adapt and accept that other cultures may communicate and do things differently.¹

How can intercultural communication be defined? Intercultural communication means communication that transcends the boundaries of essentially different cultures. Intercultural communication occurs when two or more people from different cultural backgrounds interact and communicate with each other or with each other. Intercultural communication can therefore be defined as sharing information with different levels of

¹ Arasaratnam, L.A.(2013). Intercultural Communication competence. In A.Kurylo (Ed), Intercultural Communication: Representation and construction of culture (Chap3, pp.47-68). Los Angel, CA: SAGE Publications

consciousness among people from different cultural backgrounds. Influenced individuals from different cultural groups negotiate common meanings in their interactions. You may have heard the term “intercultural communication”. This section presents some commonly accepted academic and applied definitions to clarify this concept and process. It helps scholars and practitioners clarify the meaning of certain terms. The term “intercultural communication” describes a broad range of ideas that are difficult to articulate in one direction.

In the field of intercultural business communication, a lot of people argue that culture influences how messages are encoded, the medium through which they are transmitted, and how messages are interpreted. Intercultural communication studies interactions between people from different cultural backgrounds. Intercultural communication focuses on social characteristics, thought patterns, and the cultures of various groups of people in addition to language. Understanding the languages, customs, and cultures of people from other countries is also necessary.²

How would it be significant to examine the role of history in Intercultural Communication?

Because history determines culture and cultural identities, it is essential to investigate the role that history plays in intercultural communication. Therefore, cultural behavior is influenced by history. Languages spoken, ethnicities or religions of a nation, and cultural conflicts between nations can all be determined by history. “Culture and cultural identities are intimately tied to history, as they have no meaning without history,” claim Martin and Nakayama. (Martin, J.N., and T.K. Nakayama, 2011, page 68)

Intercultural communication was coined by Leeds-Hurwitz and Edward T. Hall to shed light on intercultural relations and rule relations. Intercultural communication began in the 1960s and 1970s focusing on qualitative analyses, racial attitudes, public deliberation, cross cultural, and doctor-patient relationships (Asante et al., 2017, p.76). In the beginning, Intercultural communication was in the field of social studies and sociology. Overtime, it became known as the concept of face-to-face interactions

In 1989, Intercultural communication continued to emerge from 'scholar Ting-Toomey's identity negotiation process. Intercultural communication continued to progress with intercultural competence, the examination of identity research by way of validation. and negotiation.

² Chen, G.M., & Starosta, W.J. (1998). Foundations of intercultural communication. Boston, MA: Allyn & Bacon.

To conclude, The subject of intercultural communication discipline is the most ancient times of history and civilization of mankind, when individuals and groups from different cultures interacted in various contexts and for different reasons. Intercultural communication is necessary in regards to society because individuals need to understand how meaning is created in cultural communities and learn how to achieve agreement through interactionsю

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6. Martin, J.N., and T.K. Nakayama, 2011, page 68.
7. Moore, C., and P. Woodrow, 1998, page 1.

